

Resistance of RD4 and RD7 mutants to rice gall midge

Weerawooth Katanyukul, Entomology Department, IRRRI; Sawang Kadkao and Chintana Tayathum, Entomology and Zoology Division; and Pricha Khambanonda and Malee Chomhubol, Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand

Rice gall midge of Thailand is the most virulent biotype in Asia. Eswarakora, a rice variety from India, is the only known resistance source, but its crosses usually have poor grain quality. Because most farmers in the gall midge endemic areas have limited capital to purchase insecticide, resistant varieties are the most practical control method.

RD4, a gall midge-resistant rice variety released in 1973, did not gain popularity because it has poor cooking and eating quality. Seed was treated by gamma irradiation to improve rice quality. After selection for 9 generations, 24 lines of mutants that met grain quality standards were screened for gall midge resistance in a greenhouse at Pan Rice Experiment Station, Cheingrai, in 1980; Fourteen entries were selected and retested in 1981 in farmers' fields in Ban Parauk, Cheingrai. The experiment was in a randomized complete block with two replications. Each entry was planted

in 2 rows of 20 hills. Silvershoots from every other hill, 20 hills/entry, were counted at 40 and 60 days after transplanting (DT). Grain quality was assessed after harvest.

All 14 entries of RD4 mutants were highly resistant to gall midge. Percen-

tage of silvershoots at 60 DT ranged from 0.4 to 1.9. That for susceptible check RD1 was 20.5% (Table 1). RD4 mutants also yielded high compared to the original RD4 variety, have good grain quality, and are promising substitutes for RD4 in the glutinous rice eat-

Table 2. Rice gall midge reaction of RD7 mutants and resistant varieties in a greenhouse test at the Rice Protection Research Center, Bangkok, Thailand, 1981.^a

Mutant, variety	Silvershoots (%)	Reaction ^b
RD777G, CO-53-10-4-1	65.4	S
RD777G, CO-53-10-4-4	70.0	S
RD777G, CO-53-10-6-1	63.6	S
RD777G, CO-53-10-6-2	64.0	S
RD777G, CO-55-3-5-1	11.3	MR
RD777G, CO-77-4-1-1	51.3	S
RD777G, CO-77-9-1-1	5.9	R
RD777G, CO-317-8-1-1	54.8	S
RD777G, CO-317-8-1-2	62.9	S
RD777G, CO-317-8-1-4	53.9	S
RD777G, CO-317-8-1-5	49.5	S
RD777G, CO-317-13-6-1	51.8	S
ARC10660	51.5	S
ARC10659	50.6	S
ARC10654	45.4	S
ARC5984	45.6	S
Banglei	48.1	S
Ritiang	57.8	S
Nagarsal	57.9	S
PTB21	46.9	S
PTB18	31.2	S
Leaung 152	47.9	S
T1426	56.2	S
Eswarakora	24.1	S
W1263	9.2	MR
RD1 (susceptible check)	44.8	S
RD4 (resistant check)	12.6	MR
MN62M (resistant check)	15.5	MR

^aAV of 2 replications. ^bResistant (R) = 0-5% silvershoots, moderately resistant (MR) = 6-15%, susceptible (S) = 16% or more.

Table 1. RD4 mutant grain and yield quality and field reaction to rice gall midge, Ban Parauk, Cheingrai, 1981.^a

Mutant, variety	Silvershoots (%)		Reaction	Yield (kg/40 hills)	Grain quality ^b	
	40 DT	60 DT			Grain shape	Cooking
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-3-15-4	1.3	1.6	R	1.2	2.96	6.9
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-3-7-5	0.5	0.4	R	1.5	2.96	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-3-11-9	0.3	0.7	R	1.4	2.96	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-17-5-4	1.3	1.1	R	1.6	2.94	6.9
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-17-7-7	1.4	1.9	R	1.5	3.04	6.8
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-17-8-2	0.3	1.2	R	1.5	2.98	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-17-16-9	0.6	1.0	R	1.5	2.93	6.8
RD476-G2-CO-2-1-17-17-2	0.7	1.9	R	1.6	2.99	6.9
RD476-G2-CO-2-7-2-5-3	0.6	1.9	R	1.5	2.97	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-7-3-2-6	1.1	1.3	R	1.5	2.90	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-7-3-4-4	1.0	1.3	R	1.5	2.95	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-7-3-4-18	0.5	1.7	R	1.7	2.92	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-7-3-5-6	0.7	1.4	R	1.4	3.03	7.0
RD476-G2-CO-2-7-4-8-16	1.8	0.6	R	1.6	2.87	7.0
RD1 (susceptible check)	13.2	20.5	S	1.3	3.15	6.0
RD4 (resistant check)	1.2	2.9	R	1.6	3.00	4.0
RD9 (resistant check)	1.4	5.4	R	1.5	3.17	7.0

^aResistant (R) = 0-5% silvershoots, moderately resistant (MR) = 6-15%, susceptible (S) = 16% or more. ^bGrain shape = length and width ratio: over 3 = slender, 2.1-3.0 = medium; cooking quality (alkali digestion): 7 = very good, 6-7 = fair to good, 4-5 = poor to fair.

ing areas of north and northeast Thailand.

During 1981, 12 nonglutinous lines from RD7 mutants plus resistant varieties from India were screened in a

greenhouse at the Rice Protection Research Center, Bangkok, using gall midges from a mass rearing culture. Two RD7 mutants — RD7^{77G} CO-55-3-5-1 and RD7^{77G} CO-77-9-1-1—

were resistant to gall midge (Table 2). All Indian rice varieties except W1263 were susceptible, confirming the results of the International Gall Midge Biotype Collaborative Project. *h*

Evaluation of National Screening Nursery against rice thrips

Jaswant Singh and G. S. Dhaliwal, Punjab Agricultural University, Rice Research Station (RRS), Kapurthala-144601, Punjab, India

National Screening Nursery entries were field tested for resistance to rice thrips

Baliothrips biformis Schmutz at the RRS, Kapurthala. Thirty-five-day-old seedlings of each entry were planted 1 seedling/hill in two 5-m rows. Hills were spaced 15 × 15 cm with 20 cm between rows in each selection and 40 cm between selections. TN1 was included as the susceptible check. Entries were scored for thrips damage 20 days after transplanting (growth

stage 2) by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (1980).

Of 384 entries, 3 were scored 1; 19, 2; 107, 3; 186, 4; 59, 5; 6, 6; and 2, 7. Average score was 4. The 3 entries given a score of 1 (most resistant) were IET8200 (Hansraj/Saket 4), IET8258 (Hema/Vikram/Rajeswari/CR57-1523) and IET8283 (Tellahamsa/CR126-42-5). *h*

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Salt tolerance of mangrove swamp rice varieties

M. P. Jones and J. W. Stenhouse, Breeding Section, West African Rice Development Association (WARDA), Special Research Project, Rokupr, Sierra Leone

Development of salt-tolerant rice varieties would help stabilize rice production and make expansion of cultivable land possible in mangrove swamps of West African countries where salinity is a major limiting factor. Studies to develop

improved salt-tolerant varieties adapted to mangrove conditions were started in 1979.

A method to rapidly evaluate rice variety and breeding line salt tolerance by comparing seedling root growth in salin-

Root lengths, root increments, and tolerance ratios (TR) of salt-tolerant and some moderately tolerant mangrove swamp rice varieties^a, Rokupr, Sierra Leone.

Variety	Root length (cm) in culture solution		Root increment (cm)	Root length (cm) in 80 mM NaCl solution		Root increment (cm)	TR
	7 DS	11 DS		13 DS	17 DS		
<i>Tolerant</i>							
Pa Merr 108A	2.9	7.9	5.0	8.6	11.1	2.5	0.50
Pa Foday Yoreh 260	1.3	5.5	4.2	5.9	8.0	2.1	0.50
Gassiline 193B	1.9	6.8	4.9	6.9	9.2	2.3	0.47
Pa Fant 213	1.3	6.7	5.4	7.1	9.3	2.2	0.41
Pa Rice Mill 199	1.9	8.2	6.3	8.5	11.1	2.6	0.41
Pa Bathurst 32A	1.4	4.9	3.5	4.8	6.2	1.4	0.40
Ginsa Killing 408	1.6	7.0	5.4	7.2	9.7	2.5	0.46
Majako 334	4.8	8.5	3.7	8.7	10.4	1.7	0.46
Janeh Kano 469	2.7	6.7	4.0	6.9	8.7	1.8	0.45
Banjul Ba 355	1.8	6.2	4.4	6.5	8.3	1.8	0.41
Kaopa Wolengo 443	3.0	6.5	3.5	7.0	8.4	1.4	0.40
<i>Moderately tolerant</i>							
SR 26 ^b	2.6	7.2	4.6	8.0	9.8	1.8	0.39
BD 2 ^b	2.2	6.9	4.7	7.7	9.5	1.7	0.36
Rok 8 ^b	4.6	7.9	3.3	8.5	9.5	1.0	0.30
Rok 4 ^b	5.0	8.7	3.7	9.4	10.4	1.0	0.27
Rok 5 ^b	3.4	7.9	4.5	8.2	9.4	1.2	0.27
Rok 9 ^b	4.9	8.3	3.4	8.6	9.5	0.9	0.27
Phar Com En ^b	3.2	7.4	4.2	8.2	9.2	1.0	0.24
Atahna 311A	3.8	8.0	4.2	8.2	9.6	1.4	0.33
Pa Sorro 104A	1.8	7.7	5.9	8.8	10.1	1.3	0.22
Nkumbandingo 405	3.5	10.7	7.2	10.9	12.0	1.1	0.15
<i>Checks</i>							
Pokkali (tolerant)	5.5	10.0	4.4	10.2	12.5	2.3	0.52
IR28 (sensitive)	2.0	6.5	4.5	6.4	6.6	0.2	0.04

^aDS = days after sowing. TR = $\frac{\text{root increment over 4 days in salinized culture solution}}{\text{root increment over 4 days in nonsalinized culture solution}}$. ^bRecommended variety.